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Electricity Production Per Capita at a Global Level

Grew on average by 3.22% between 2013 and 2022

The indicator “Electricity output, GWh/mn pop.” measures a country's electricity production in gigawatt-hours (GWh) per million inhabitants. This indicator represents the amount of electrical energy produced by a country, normalized per million inhabitants. It is expressed in gigawatt-hours (GWh) per million inhabitants. The formula to calculate the indicator is as follows: $\text{Electricity Output (GWh/mn pop)} = (\text{Total Electricity Production (GWh)}) / (\text{Country Population (in millions)})$. Data on total electricity production can be obtained from national government energy agencies, international organizations such as the International Energy Agency (IEA), or other energy statistics sources. Population data is generally collected by national statistics agencies, censuses, and international bodies such as the United Nations or the World Bank. It is a key indicator of a country's level of development and innovation. Higher electricity production per million inhabitants can indicate a more advanced energy infrastructure and a greater capacity to support innovative economic and industrial activities. It provides information on the energy efficiency and sustainability of electricity production in relation to population size. It allows for comparison of electricity production capacity between different countries, taking into account their population, facilitating the identification of best practices and areas for improvement. High values indicate that the country has relatively high electricity production compared to its population, suggesting abundant energy availability that can support economic and technological development. Low values indicate relatively low electricity production compared to the population, which could be a limitation for economic development and innovation. In summary, this indicator provides insight into a country's ability to produce electricity proportionate to its population, a crucial aspect for assessing its potential for innovation and sustainable development.

Source: Global Innovation Index

Link: <https://prosperitydata360.worldbank.org/en/indicator/WIPO+GII+64>

Electricity production per capita at a global level in 2022. The analysis of per capita electricity production globally in 2022 highlights significant differences among various countries, reflecting economic, infrastructural, and technological development disparities. At the top of the list are Bahrain, Iceland, and Norway, each with a per capita electricity production of 100 GWh per million inhabitants. These countries benefit from abundant natural resources and advanced infrastructure.

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Iceland, for example, extensively utilizes its geothermal resources, while Norway primarily uses hydroelectric power. Kuwait and Qatar, with 87.5 and 86.4 GWh per million inhabitants respectively, show how rich oil and natural gas resources can translate into high electricity production. Canada and Sweden, with 82.7 and 77 GWh respectively, demonstrate the effectiveness of their energy policies combining hydroelectric and nuclear power to meet domestic demand. The United Arab Emirates and the United States, with 69.5 and 62.8 GWh per million inhabitants, show the impact of their large economies and advanced energy infrastructure. South Korea and Saudi Arabia, both with a production of 55.1 GWh per million inhabitants, reflect their strong industrial development and commitment to fossil and nuclear energy. Australia and Singapore, with 50.5 and 46 GWh per million inhabitants respectively, represent developed economies with high electricity demand to support their technological and industrial infrastructure. Japan and Slovenia, with 39.9 and 39.4 GWh per million inhabitants respectively, demonstrate the intensive use of energy resources and advanced technologies to maintain electricity production. France, Austria, and Belgium, with respective values of 38.2, 38, and 37.3 GWh per million inhabitants, highlight the importance of nuclear and renewable energy in their energy mix. The Russian Federation and Germany, with 36.8 and 33.9 GWh per million inhabitants, show the crucial role of fossil and nuclear resources in their energy production. Latin American countries such as Paraguay, Trinidad and Tobago, and Uruguay, with production values ranging from 32.4 to 18.4 GWh per million inhabitants, reflect the use of hydroelectric and fossil resources to meet domestic demand. Brazil and Mexico, with 14.2 and 13.2 GWh per million inhabitants, highlight the importance of hydroelectric and fossil resources in their energy mix. Southeast Asian countries such as Vietnam, Thailand, and Indonesia, with production values between 12 and 5 GWh per million inhabitants, show rapid economic growth but still limited energy production compared to more developed countries. India, with 5.6 GWh per million inhabitants, reflects its enormous energy needs to support a rapidly growing population, despite challenges in energy production and distribution. Sub-Saharan Africa, with extremely low values, such as Nigeria (0.6 GWh) and Ethiopia (0.5 GWh), highlights deep infrastructural and energy access challenges that limit economic and social development. In summary, the data shows how per capita electricity production is closely correlated with economic development, available natural resources, and the energy policies adopted by individual countries. While developed countries boast high production due to advanced infrastructure and abundant energy resources, many developing countries face significant challenges in meeting energy demand, which can hinder their economic and social progress. These disparities underscore the importance of global policies aimed at improving energy access and promoting sustainable development worldwide.

Electricity production per capita at a global level between 2013 and 2022. Global electricity production has undergone significant variations between 2013 and 2022, with different countries showing notable increases or decreases in percentages and absolute values. Starting with the countries with the highest percentage growth, Botswana recorded an increase of 340%, rising from 1.0 to 4.4. Another notable case is Cambodia, with an increase of 733.33%, although the absolute value is modest, from 0.3 to 2.5. Moldova also showed an impressive growth of 142.55%, increasing from 4.7 to 11.4. These increases are significant for countries that started from a low base of electricity production. In terms of absolute growth, China leads with an increase of 12.2, rising from 14.9 to 27.1, followed by Saudi Arabia with an increase of 13.1, from 42 to 55.1. The increase in production in China is particularly relevant given its already large initial scale, underscoring the country's continued industrial and urban development. Vietnam also saw substantial growth of 6.8, from 5.2 to 12, indicating robust economic growth and rising energy demand. Conversely, several countries

recorded decreases in both absolute value and percentage. The most significant percentage decrease was observed in Yemen, with a reduction of 66.67%, from 1.5 to 0.5, likely due to conflicts and political instability that compromised energy infrastructure. Estonia also showed a drastic decline of 55.19%, falling from 46.2 to 20.7, reflecting possible changes in energy policies or demand. The highest absolute decrease was in Canada, with a reduction of 6.0, from 88.7 to 82.7, followed by Kuwait with a loss of 12.5, from 100 to 87.5. Among countries with moderate reductions, Germany recorded a decline of 1.9, from 35.8 to 33.9, and the United Kingdom saw a decrease of 5.2, from 27.8 to 22.6. These reductions could be linked to increased energy efficiency, a transition to renewable sources, or changes in energy production policies. Some countries maintained stable production, with minimal variations. For example, electricity production in Switzerland increased by only 0.1, from 38.6 to 38.7, while in Japan it grew by 0.2, from 39.7 to 39.9. This suggests stability in these countries' energy sectors, which may already be highly developed and efficient. It is interesting to note how some countries increased their production despite complex economic or political situations. For instance, Iran increased its production by 3.8, from 15.1 to 18.9, showing an expansion of the energy sector despite international economic sanctions. Bangladesh also showed notable growth of 84.62%, from 1.3 to 2.4, indicating significant development in its energy infrastructure. In Europe, countries like Austria, Belgium, and Spain experienced mixed changes. Austria increased production by 2.4, from 35.6 to 38, while Spain saw a reduction of 3.5, from 30.2 to 26.7. These changes reflect different approaches to energy policies, with some countries pushing for greater production while others seek to reduce output or make their grids more efficient. The Middle East also shows interesting dynamics. While Bahrain nearly doubled its production, rising from 50.4 to 100, with an increase of 98.41%, Kuwait reduced production by 12.5%, from 100 to 87.5. These data may reflect differences in energy resource management strategies and responses to domestic and external demand. In Latin America, countries like Argentina and Brazil recorded modest increases of 4.73% and 12.70% respectively, while Chile saw a more marked increase of 13.19%, from 18.2 to 20.6. These increases suggest growing energy demand in these developing economies. Finally, some African countries recorded significant percentage increases. Ethiopia, for example, saw a 150% increase, although in absolute terms it is modest, rising from 0.2 to 0.5. This indicates a notable effort to improve access to electricity, although starting from a very low base. In summary, the data shows a varied global landscape where electricity production is influenced by a combination of economic, political, and technological factors. While some countries have significantly increased their production to meet growing demand or improve infrastructure, others have reduced production in response to energy efficiency policies, demand changes, or political instability. These dynamics reflect the complex interactions between economic development, energy policies, and infrastructure capacity at a global level.

Conclusions. Electricity production per capita grew on average by 3.22% between 2013 and 2022 for the countries analyzed. There are countries where the value of electricity production per capita has grown much more than the period average, namely: Cambodia with +733.33%, Botswana with +340.00%, Ethiopia with +150.00%, Moldova with +142.55%, Vietnam with +130.77%. There are also countries where the value of electricity production per capita has decreased significantly, namely North Macedonia with -26.04%, Namibia with -38.71%, Estonia with -55.19%, Luxembourg with -61.07%, Yemen with -66.67%.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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